

EVANGELIZATION IN THE PLURALISTIC SOCIETY OF ASIA

Abp. Thomas MENAMPARAMPIL SDB

The author <menamabp@gmail.com> served as Bishop and Archbishop in Dibrugarh (1981-92), Guwahati (1992-2012), and Jowai (2014-16). He is a revered champion of peace and reconciliation. He is a prolific writer and is a regular contributor to our Journal.

Abstract: In post-colonial times, newly liberated nations have an eagerness to assert their cultures, religions and value-systems. It is only when the Evangelizer develops the ability to bridge cultural distances does he/she acquire the persuasive power required for proposing Gospel solutions to diverse human problems. Such proposals, even under a secular garb, can powerfully point to Jesus. He will be most effective when he influences thought-provokers, opinion-shapers, and value-setters in society. Such a deeper sharing is possible only in contexts of ‘intimacy’.

Keywords: Culture-translators, Gospel in Secular Vocabulary, Intimate Sharing, Whispering, Evangelization, Pluralism, Asian Christianity.

1. CHRISTIAN COMMUNITY: A FORCE FOR GOOD IN SOCIETY

1.1 Self-assertion of Nations (Communities) in Asia

In the post-colonial era, the first emphasis of every newly liberated Asian nation has been the assertion of its identity, culture, and value-system. The more their heritage has been challenged, the more earnestly have Asian nations been exploring ways of reasserting it in new ways. For example, we hear of the revival of Confucian ethos, Hindu traditions, cultural patrimony, ethnic legacy, religious fidelity... and of late, of *Cultural Nationalism*.

Asians know for certain that *cultural rootlessness cannot contribute anything* to the future of Asia. They are too proud

of their civilizational heritage to sell it away for a bowl of soup (Gen 25:27-34), for mere Market advantages. After all, Economy is not everything. “Man does not live on bread alone” (Lk 4:4). However, the temptation remains.

1.2 Self-assertion of Religions

Partly in a reaction to exaggerated forms of secularization in the West, Asian societies, while building up their economic strength, have been re-asserting their *religious traditions* sturdily. Temples and mosques keep rising high on the Continent. To the surprise of Western intellectuals, the younger generation in Asia clings to their faith with greater intensity than ever before, even going to the point of radicalism. *People throng to pilgrim-centres* – including Christian shrines – by the million. Prayer-houses, meditation centres become visible at every corner.

Unfortunately, in these forms of religious revival one does not notice a distinction being made between what is genuinely spiritual and what is a turn to the archaic, between what is religiously inspired and what is merely a veiled assertion of political interest. In several contexts, *religion* is being *instrumentalized for political goals*. It would rather look as though the ‘collective unconscious’ of societies is having a free play after a long period of its humiliation and suppression.

1.3 Core Concerns of Asian Civilizations

Asian minds have always exercised their creativity on questions of *suffering and its causes*, renunciation and its various expressions, community and an individual’s obligations within it, the furthest reaches of egolessness, respect for all sentient things, reverence for nature, control of the mind, practice of non-violence, living of orderly lives in family and society, striving for harmony and unity amidst diversity and contradictions, and the true nature of the Ultimate.

No matter how enthusiastic we become about modernization and globalization, and the ideologies that oppose them, it is only when we touch the *core concerns of*

a civilization do we touch the *SOUL of a people* and come on the wavelength of the masses. Only when we address the deepest aspirations of a society or of a community, do we evoke an adequate response. Unfortunately, many Christian Missionaries, while being usefully engaged, remain peripheral to the core concerns of the civilization or specific culture they are addressing the Gospel to.

In his conversation with the Samaritan woman, Jesus knew how to move from a request for an immediate need (his thirst to be quenched) to *spiritual depth*. “If you only knew the Gift of God” (Jn 4:10). A threefold barrier stood between her and Jesus: the fact that she was a sinner, a woman, and a *Samaritan*. However, it became evident that ‘the gift of God’ *transcends cultures*, crosses frontiers, breaks barriers, *removes prejudices*, mellows opposition, and changes hearts. Thus, the Missionary comes close to the heart of the individual or community to whom he/she is addressing the Gospel. That *intimacy is the bridge* over which the message of the Gospel moves from one heart to another.

1.4 Loyal Christians, Committed Citizens

One danger we must specially guard against is that we, Christians in Asia, must not become strangers in our own country, having distanced ourselves from our cultural roots and the concerns of our communities. This danger is often evident in those who have studied or worked abroad for several years, having become over-influenced by western outlook and value-systems or even by the apostolic approaches of certain insensitive Christian groups. The *Christian minority* must make sure that they are fully inserted into the social fabric of their nation and are *sincerely committed to the betterment of the community* to which they belong. They should wholeheartedly be involved with the issues their people are anxious about.

This means awakening a deeper sense of *Christian responsibility to help society* (nation, community) to address the problems and anxieties of the present day and immediate context: political exploitation, violence, corruption, damage

to environment, weakening of ethical values, irresponsibility, crass materialism, abortion, euthanasia, economic inequality, unfairness to weaker sections, erosion of cultures, erosion of traditional values, breakdown of family, etc. Mere denunciation will not help much. Christian workers should invite fellow citizens to think responsibly and intelligently, and take on responsibility.

A special dimension of our mission today is to *invite fellow citizens to think together* responsibly and cooperate with their constructive initiatives. Speaking to young people at Rio de Janeiro in 2013, Pope Francis raised his voice, “I want the Church to get out into the street, I want us to avoid... being closed in upon ourselves.” Pope Francis wanted a Church that continuously looked out for an opportunity to *reach out helpfully to the people*, most of all *those at the periphery*: those at the geographical, psychological, social, cultural, religious margins.

1.5 Christians Should Stand with Leaders Who Uphold Values

As citizens in a democratic state, we have a national responsibility. In a globalized world, we have a global responsibility. Committed Christian citizens cultivate this sense of universal responsibility in themselves and foster it in others. They have a duty to insist with the persons they have elected to maintain a sense of dignity about what they say or do and act responsibly, and *demand from them a code of conduct*, a style of behaviour, a manner of approach to persons and issues in keeping with that dignity, and expect from them a degree of commitment to the concerns of the people as long as they hold office.

We are living in an era when democracy is collapsing even in traditionally democratic countries. Even people, who accept electoral democracy, are often illiberal,¹ prejudiced against racial minorities, immigrants, or people of other religions. Hate speeches are on the increase in the social

¹ Yascha Mounk, *The People Vs. Democracy* (Cambridge, MA – London: Harvard University Press, 2018), 8.

media.² *Making democracies function as democracies* itself has become a great mission. Jesus' Message must become incarnate in our days to transform and *rejuvenate the world in contexts*. It must address the problems of warped democracy, abuse of power, distorted media, inter-community conflicts, human trafficking, deforestation, threat to environment, mounting inequality, and widespread corruption.

As Vaclav Havel, the Czech leader, who was struggling against a powerful Communist regime in Czechoslovakia, said, "We all can and must do something" for effecting a change. "No one else can do it for us, so we can't wait for someone else."³ It is in this context he cried, "Words still have power." So, let us *read, write, speak*, teach, relate, discuss, debate, and discover what is best for our society. Share those insights with others. *Awaken a Sense of Responsibility*. Exert a healthy influence in society. Guide the thought of intellectuals. Shape the thinking in our community.

1.6 Influencing the 'Thinking Element in Society'

We should work hard to make sure that *right thinking prevails in Universities* where thoughts about the future are shaped, *Legislatures* where policies for social betterment are formulated, *Media* through which truthful information is distributed, *Markets* on which the livelihood of millions depends, and many other areas where human beings interact, contend, and struggle against each other, or help, encourage, motivate, and sustain one another.

I would like to suggest that we influence an important element in society that I would describe as the "Thinking Element": *thought-provokers, opinion-shapers, value-setters, goal-proposers, ideals-planters, vision-projectors, energy-sustainers, soul-inspirers*. These are persons who *give to a people a collective "self-understanding"* as a society and maintain its stamina for the future. They set the goals towards which it keeps moving. They correct the aberrations that creep into their society's style of thinking,

² Mounk, *The People Vs. Democracy*, 17.

³ Vaclav Havel, *Disturbing the Peace* (New York: Vintage Books, 1991), 12.

living, or relating. They strike new ground while seeking to remain true to its core identity.

If Christian intellectuals and *missionaries* could find a place among them, they could legitimately claim to be the “salt of the earth,” at least in a manner of speaking. I would place among such “Thinking Element” in society thinkers, poets, writers, professors, journalists, composers, *artists, speakers, inspirers*, religious leaders, and several such people. To the extent they keep their goals sublime, they win the admiration of the intellectuals; to the extent that they remain truly “human,” they win the enthusiastic support of the masses. I wish we could win the attention of these two categories of people.

It is when *Missionaries* have entered into companionship with such stalwarts that they gain a certain *moral authority in a society*. In the present context of serving the larger society in a multi-religious and secular situation, this is a realistic goal towards which we can seek to move at the present stage. *Human values of natural goodness*, an eagerness to search for truth, a sense of solidarity, an urge towards generosity, sincerity of purpose, and concern for others *remain buried in every heart*, even though in today’s self-centred world they may have sunk deeper. They need to be dug up and their resources fully tapped.

2. POINTING TO JESUS

2.1 Gradualness in the Discovery of Jesus’ Identity

Despite all that we have discussed above, our obligation to point to Jesus remains. “Woe to me If I do not *preach the Gospel*,” cried Paul (1 Cor 9:16). No doubt, for most people, the discovery that Jesus as the Son of God is a gradual process. Nicodemus reached the point of seeing in Jesus a *teacher*, though very special. He said, “Rabbi, we know that you are a teacher sent by God. No one could perform the miracles you are doing unless God were with him” (Jn 3:2). Many people thought of him as *John the Baptist, Elijah, Jeremiah*, or one of the prophets. The Samaritan woman saw him as a prophet, “I see you

are a *prophet*, sir,” while wondering whether he was the Messiah (Jn 4:19).

However, Peter’s faith is clear, “You are the Christ, the *Son of the living God*” (Jn 16:16). Nathaniel breaks down: “You are the Son of God! You are the King of Israel” (Jn 1:49).

We need to allow this gradualness its due course, every person or community at its own pace of search and its own manner of discovery. A spiritual conversation is like an Emmaus walk. The final *discovery of Jesus may come as a surprise*. There is many a God-seeker in Asia who is looking for a companion and a guide on the way to Emmaus. He/she wants a God-experienced person to go with him/her and show the way. *A deeper encounter with Jesus* can be staggering. Thomas exclaimed, “My Lord and my God” (Jn 20:28). A look from Jesus drew tears from Peter (Lk 22:62).

The first important thing, then, is that there should be *someone to explain*. And the second thing is that the Evangelizer starts from where the Inquirer is: his/her state of mind, *his/her immediate problem*, the level of his/her understanding, the aspirations of his/her heart, the quotation from Scriptures that has inspired him/her, *configurations of his/her culture*, the limitations of his/her horizon and vision.

2.2 Pressing Needs of the Moment Is an Insertion Point

Jesus often began by giving attention to a *pressing need* of a person (leper, blind man) or a community (suffering injustice). Not rarely he was speaking to crowds that were “*harassed and helpless*” (Mt 9:36) against the Roman exploiters and the Jewish elite that took advantage of their weakness. They were like sheep without a shepherd. It was in his preference for them that Jesus differed from the Scribes and Pharisees. His message was extremely relevant to the distressed. And they responded. “What is this?” they asked. “A new teaching!” (Mk 1:27). The newness and attention winning power of his teaching were not so much due to the quality of its eloquence or rhetoric as to its immediate relevance to people’s needs. The words he said and

deeds he performed addressed the felt needs of individuals and communities with whom he was seeking to relate.

Relevance, timeliness, and purposefulness of a Message open the hearts and minds of all people to whom it is addressed. Its personal tone and emotion-charged expressions add unction to the Message. It *kindles fire in hearts*. Jesus was not calling for a revolution, he was giving them hope. Words have power; they have a transformative quality. The world is eager for a radical change.

A missionary's concerns are about the needs of the *weak and the marginalized*. He/she attends primarily to people under tension.⁴ He/she seeks to *sustain their hope*, sharing the Message contained in these words of Jesus, "Blessed are you when men revile you and persecute you and utter all kinds of evil against you falsely..." (Mt 5:11).

3. OVERCOMING CULTURAL DISTANCES

3.1 Cultural Boundaries to be Crossed

Veteran Evangelizers in Asia will tell us that certain evangelical approaches are in bad taste: arguments in general; claims of superiority; *aggressive evangelistic crusades* and campaigns; condemnation of other religions or their traditions; ridiculing of their beliefs or the symbols they use; claims of impressive Christian numbers or achievements; going across cultures and 'convicting people of sin'; ignoring cultural sensitivities in general.

I would like to emphasize especially the point of 'culture.' We need to study with keen interest how the Gospel crossed cultural boundaries in different periods of history: *Jesus* speaking to the Samaritan woman, the Syro-phoenician woman, and the Roman officer; *St. Paul* addressing the Athenians, Roman officers, indigenous people of Asia Minor and the islands; *St. Patrick* preaching to the Celts, *St. Boniface* to the Saxons, *St. Francis Xavier* to the fisher-folk of Malabar Coast, *Fr. Constant Lievens* to the tribal people of Chota Nagpur.

⁴ Rick Warren, *Purpose Driven Church* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1995), 182-183.

Those Missionaries, like Patrick or Boniface, who quickly *identified themselves with the community* to whom they were addressing the Gospel, won a hearing; they drew new adherents to the Christian faith, and built up self-reliant Churches. Through their creativity and the collaboration of indigenous communities, faith developed new forms of expressing itself in thought, art, music, worship, organization, and other cultural self-expressions that edified the rest of the Universal Church.

3.2 Take Careful Note of Cultural Expressions

Some of the details I refer to below may look trivial, but in day-to-day life, they are significant. Every community has its own *way of showing familiarity or displeasure*, surprise or shock, concern or compassion, cordial welcome or total indifference, acceptance or rejection. These feelings are expressed at times explicitly in words, at other times through indirect hints. Some prefer to be more indicative than vocal, to suggest than to pronounce, to express their meaning in silence or *body language* (shaking of heads, lifting eyebrows, smiling, or frowning) than state clearly or affirm strongly.

Certain serious matters are whispered in the ear, not proclaimed from housetops. The West usually likes to be frank; the East seeks not to offend. The manner in which children relate with their parents, younger members interact with their elders, boys mix with girls, the way they all *show respect to seniors* or religious persons, will be different according to the different traditions of each community.

You can make serious mistakes by being *too assertive* where a *gentler approach* is more acceptable to a community, or by leaving everything to people's initiative where a more direct involvement may be necessary. What appears to one community as respectful and dignified may appear cold and reserved to another. What looks to one as self-confident and expansive may look to another as arrogant and interfering. Reward or punishment, or the way of administering them may be different. The manner of eliciting help, evoking collaboration, offering scope for participation, *seeking*

assent, expressing dissent, perception of time, emphasis on punctuality, role of the individual in family and society, position of adults, the manner of addressing each other ... all these are culturally conditioned.

One enjoys using *understatements* (euphemisms), another delights in *overstatements*. When South Europeans describe a performance as ‘fantastic,’ ‘fabulous,’ ‘incredible,’ an Englishman may refer to the same event as ‘tolerably good’ or say that it was ‘not too bad,’ or ‘fairly good.’ Only one who is acquainted with these differences will know how to interpret the remark in its own context.

Similarly, there is something like the *collective mood of a community/society/nation* in a particular period of history: e.g., *after a war*, in periods of ethnic conflicts or social chaos, of *economic boom* or economic recession; in contexts of violence, of rampant corruption; when emerging from under a totalitarian regime. Vocabulary used and approaches adopted will necessarily need to be different; one will have to pay attention to differences in the meaning of words used, programmes launched, celebrations held, discipline imposed, according to *varying moods and situations*.

3.3 Sensitivities Differ

Let us take an example. With rapid secularization, the West today gives far greater importance to freedom of expression than respect for religious sentiments. *For Asians* this is a wrong sense of order. For them, *religious sensitivity comes first*. Even a Marxist in India, despite his/her claim to believe only in scientific materialism, would not dare to ridicule a religious belief, a holy book, a sacred text, or a noble Prophet. The West has no such inhibitions. *Ignoring this cultural difference* has led to many painful consequences. The recent controversies around *The Last Temptation*, *The Sixth Wound*, and *Da Vinci Code* with reference to Christ, and *Satanic Verses*, *Danish Cartoons*, and similar things in reference to Mohammed, highlight the difference. Sadly, these cartoons were published repeatedly. Priests, religious, and *westernized Asian*

intellectuals who have become alienated from their own cultures can make similar mistakes.

‘We Westerners like to be frank,’ said a Western spokesperson after Pope Benedict XVI’s Regensburg speech. Is that really true? But woe to you if you are too frank using words that are politically incorrect, words that seem to claim *racial superiority* or express *gender bias*. You would be preparing yourself for disaster, if you make any comments that are not ‘*politically correct*’ about homosexual behaviour, premarital sex, same gender marriages, cohabitation, or ‘superstitions.’ Please do not use the word blind for the ‘visually impaired’ individuals, handicapped for the ‘differently abled’ persons, old for ‘senior citizens.’ ‘Backward’ countries became ‘under-developed’ countries for a while, then ‘developing’ countries.

Muslim girls cling to the use of scarf in France, Muslim men to that of the fez hat in some Arab countries. The *dhoti* or the *salwar kameez*, the beard or the sword, the Korean *kimchi* or the Khasi *thurungbai*, the Hindu beef-free food or Muslim pork-free diet...we do not know what *a community can become sensitive* about at a given time, or what it decides to make the symbol of its identity in a particular context. Blessed are the watchful and the perceptive! They can avert an extremist attack, diffuse tensions, restore calm, rebuild confidence, construct new bridges, and point a way forward to a society.

3.4 St. Paul Was a Bridge-builder

I would like to highlight an important dimension of St. Paul’s personality: he was a *builder of bridges* between the *Hebrew and Hellenic cultures*, between Asia and Europe; in fact, he himself formed a bridge between cultures, races, and civilizations. He was open to diverse communities, differing ways, habits, customs, attitudes, patterns of thought, and styles of organization. Cosmopolitan in outlook and of unlimited versatility and breadth of vision, Paul was able to come on the wavelength of the Jews, Greeks, Romans, barbarians, rabbis, philosophers, army men, jailers, businessmen, and women. His *images* were taken from *Roman city life*, scenes

of intense human energy: soldier in armour, athlete in the arena, triumphant procession of victorious generals. Notice the difference: Jesus speaking to Galileans took images from their countryside: farmers, seeds, trees, flowers, lilies, birds, sheep; sowing, reaping, serving a cruel master.

A genuine Evangelizer identifies oneself with the *deepest aspirations of the people* to whom he/she is addressing the Gospel and radically commits oneself to their fulfilment. Paul was proud to be a Roman citizen (Acts 16:37-39; 22:24-30; 25:9-12). He was proud of the Empire (Rom 13:1- 5; 1 Tim 2:1-3). He was immersed in Greek and Roman thought. He had benefited from the intellectual ferment of Tarsus, a University City, where ideas clashed and stimulated progress of thought. He had been exposed to Stoic and Epicurean philosophies.

It is only an Evangelizer rooted in the ancient wisdom and spiritual traditions of the community one is evangelizing and capable of *building on their native resources*, will be effective in presenting the Gospel. But he/she must equally *be open to fresh ideas* from anywhere else in the world. There is an ancient Indian saying, “Let noble thoughts come to us from every side” (*Rig Veda* I-89-i). Paul exclaimed, “I take every thought captive and make it obey” Christ (2 Cor 10:5). In Paul, the two distinct identities found perfect harmony.

3.5 Build Bridges to Communicate Effectively

All I am trying to say is that we need to pay attention to different categories of thought and ways of understanding, different symbols of meaning and communication, different sensitivities and emotional attachments if we want to live and work together. If you are seeking to communicate the Message across cultures and persuade the members of other communities, you must take those logical steps and establish those *thought-links that people* to whom you are addressing the Gospel *will find intelligible and convincing*. If you are writing to please, you must adopt those literary and artistic devices that in their culture and usage they find *interesting*. If entertainment is your aim, you must go for ways and styles that in their tradition are considered entertaining. We need

to adopt a different style for serious or light expressions, religious or secular material, tragic or hilarious contexts.

The contemplatively inclined *Brahmin society* admires in Christianity its experience in God-search, *mystical depth*, *spiritual earnestness*, speculative quality, and capacity for renunciation. They appreciate the contribution that the Missionaries have made towards the revival and strengthening of the dominant culture: the study of the ancient texts, the composition of dictionaries and grammars, and similar services. The more *pragmatic middle castes* may appreciate in Christian Missionaries their *efficiency*, *fruitfulness*, *cultural output*, credibility and reliability, productive habits. The *lower castes and tribal communities* are more likely to value their dedication to the poor, effectiveness in social assistance, commitment to justice, attention to their grievances, giving an utterance to their anxieties, closeness to their communities, fostering of their religious sense, and respect for their traditions.

Very importantly, *respect a community's* identity, culture, self-pride, and *unique heritage*. If anything we do appears like a threat to its selfhood, we are bound to face trouble. *Jesus comes to enhance* all that is positive in a particular culture and *lead it to perfection*, not to weaken or eliminate anything valuable.

In the same way, never allow the external things linked with Christianity (like administrative tasks, imposition of discipline, strengthening of organization, ordering of structures) to weaken your commitment to the *central concerns of humanity*: justice, peace, mercy, forgiveness, fidelity, honesty, integrity, authenticity, generosity, compassion, filial piety, respect for life. Similarly, while emphasizing marginal issues, never bypass the *core concerns of religion*: God experience, renunciation, repentance, spiritual earnestness, evangelical zeal. However, above all, draw people to the '*person of Jesus.*'

3.6 Relationship Styles Differ in Different Cultures

Ceremonies and decorations, colours and sounds are at one level of existence, life and relationships at another.

The manner in which *children relate with their parents*, younger members relate with their elders, the way they all *show respect to the Priest*, will be different according to the tradition of each community. When a Priest/Sister, after working for a number of years with one community, moves on to take up responsibility with another, he/she can make serious mistake, e.g., *taking offense where no offense is meant*.

If you are not constantly observant, unfailingly attentive to casual and spontaneous remarks and occasional outbursts of temper, you will begin to *move from one mistake to another*. You may not realize how important a birthday or an anniversary may be for some people or a commemoration of the dead for some others. The manner of dealing with people while organizing work or visiting families will be different according to differing cultural traditions.

The legitimate way of showing *familiarity or respect will differ* from community to community. The *mode of consulting* and the measure of consensus expected will vary with traditions. What is important to note is that, as individuals have different ways, communities have *different traditions and tastes*, priorities, *prejudices*, and *perceptions*.

3.7 The Usual Mistake in the Area of Culture

Culture-related mistakes can be of different kinds. The most common one is to look at others through *your own cultural glasses* and make negative judgments and be guided solely by your own cultural perceptions. Another mistake is to take on the ways of *thinking of the dominant group* in a nation/region with whom you are familiar, and evaluate everyone else according to the norms they provide. And a third form of mistake is to carry with you the cultural habits of the community you were working with earlier and annoy everyone else.

Joan Chittister, OSB, in *The Fire in these Ashes*, refers to another kind of mistake in the context of Religious Life. She was targeting the exaggerations of Modern culture: “Religious life comes out of a culture to challenge it.” *Challenging Modern Culture and its aberrations is a gigantesque task*. It is easier to yield to its weaknesses than

add to its strength. It is before this challenge that Religious Life has suffered today! Chittister says, “In some periods of history religious congregations energized the culture around them; in other periods they simply reflected culture at its worst... Religious life must be a conscious and creative response to the culture in which it exists.”

It is before these challenges we feel unequal and break down, clinging helplessly to one world or the other and to its weaknesses, *unable to become bridge-builders between cultures and agents of dialogue and reflection*, refusing to remain constant learners and stimulators of thought, failing to offer the insights of the Gospel where it is needed most. The *tragedy* is that very many Missionaries are underperforming, despite their competence, good will, and commitment, due to their non-insertion into the cultural world where they have generously accepted to serve.

4. EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION OF THE GOSPEL

4.1 The Pedagogy of Communication

A pedagogic approach may be summarized in this manner. In communicating the Faith with a person of another culture, we should take concepts and categories from the other person’s cultural world, *begin with the premises he/she would concede*, quote the authorities from his/her tradition, adopt codes of conduct and ethical principles that he/she understands and respects. And step by step we lead the enquirer from his/her own specific tradition *to a neutral cultural ground*, which means, to concepts, values, and authorities which have general acceptance in the wider world. It is only at the final stage do we *bring him/her into our own cultural world*. Even so, there should be no haste in closing ourselves in that limited world which seems to be shrinking all the time. Once bridges are removed and doors closed, no further admission will be possible.

The stages in this pilgrimage that I have just described are not so much chronological as *pedagogical*. When we are offering the gift of the Gospel to various categories of

people, the *pace of progress and styles of approach will differ* according to each person's mental preparedness, *psychological openness or resistance*. We should never forget that there is a Pedagogy of Communication in presenting the Faith, which ought to be based on the *religious psychology* of each community/person. We need to be creative, leading each person from what is *familiar to what is less familiar*, linking new ideas with what is old in each person's tradition.

Radical changes, introduced in haste, can cause a sense of insecurity and fear, and even good suggestions may be resisted or rejected. Generally, we will find it easier to win acceptance for new ideas, (i) if they are presented in a *vocabulary drawn from the ordinary parlance* of the day and with images taken from the prevalent culture, (ii) if we establish a relationship between the *old and the new*, and (iii) if we build *bridges linking proposed ideas with people's needs*.

If presenting the Gospel to people of different schools of thought within the same civilization is hard enough, offering it to persons of different cultures and civilizations will be even more difficult. Distances are far greater. The *Greeks looked for wisdom* and the *Jews for miracles* (1 Cor 1:22). The *West* may feel drawn to what is *logical and analytical*, the *East* to what is *mystical and integrative*, South (Africa, Latin America) may be exuberant and enthusiastic, and North may like to base their decisions on *existential realities*.

Similarly, Pentecostals may be *exuberant and self-expressive*, contemplatives may be often silent and generally *soft-spoken*, while communicating a serious Message at a profoundly personal level. *Intellectuals and masses* in every community differ. Young people who are tired of the same old tales, tiresome traditions, bothersome admonitions, may be looking for *something new and refreshing*. Be attentive. Be creative.

4.2 Attend to a Community's Collective Memory

The meaning of words, response to problems, reaction to authority, cooperation or resistance to leadership are shaped by a community's concepts and collective experiences in

that particular era. For example, a new *collective mood* was awakened in the *Western World by the September 11 tragedy* a couple of decades ago. Our understanding of reality and the apostolic initiatives that we adopt in response, need to take such facts into consideration. We ought to respond to the changing needs, moods, limitations and also possibilities in a new culture.

Nearly all communities have *negative memories of hurts* received in the past as a nation, ethnic or religious group, real or imagined. Holocaust, Hiroshima, Kosovo, Ayodhya are examples. *Reduction of collective anger*, removal of prejudices, smoothening of relationships, these are great services that religious personnel can offer, though success is not easy to achieve. But an effort can be made. Miracles do happen.

If in a Parish, the faithful have felt that the persons whose role was to animate and guide the community have been taking advantage of their position, or were more concerned about *imposing discipline than encouraging the weak*, or that they lacked moral fibre, the negative response over a period of time can come to have a cumulative effect. And if, a confrontational situation remains on, the resulting tension can go beyond proportions. May be, we are experiencing something of it in the Western world today. The same ailment can catch up with the new, enthusiastic, young Churches in due time. Being aware of this danger, we can prevent it as well.

In relationship styles, we can learn a lot from Paul, who, when making the challenging demands took an attitude of extreme humility, “By the gentleness and the kindness of Christ *I beg you*” (2 Cor 10:1).

5. ENSURING PASTORAL FRUITFULNESS

5.1 Different Pastoral Situations

When as a Missionary you are transferred from one place to another, there is need to learn the traditions and practices prevalent in the new place. Leave your petty interests behind and bring with you your creative enthusiasm so that you can put your new place on fire with Christ’s Message. Jesus said, “I came to set fire on earth, and how I wish it were already

kindled!” (Lk 12:49). There is nothing like going to *meet persons who are keeping a distance* from the Church... conversing, showing concern about their own personal/family interests, entering into a dialogue, resolving issues and bringing them back to a normal relationship with the Church. For everyone who returns to the flock, be sure, there will be great rejoicing in heaven (Lk 15:7).

Further, be attentive when the Holy Spirit invites you to *go out and meet new people* (Acts 10:19): contacting, not only new villages, but new tribes and communities which are open to the Gospel. Village visiting is a great ministry: visiting homes, giving instructions to the community, catechism lessons to children in preparation for the Sacraments and to young couples before their marriage. *Make new contacts*, instruct catechumens, bring together broken families, dialogue with stubborn dissenters. Develop the skill to request, urge, insist, beg, plead, convince (words that are found in Paul’s letters), to change people’s minds, and reconcile them to the Lord.

Associations like the Legion of Mary, youth organizations, parents’ federation, or women’s groups and sodalities can become *powerful agents of Evangelization* and pastoral follow-up. They have proved themselves to be active agents to ensure the success of annual festivities, monthly commemorations, or more frequent Church events.

5.2 Service in the Field of Education and Health

If you are at the service of Education, Health, or Development, take care to avoid an *‘institutional mentality’*: keeping people at a distance, developing a *‘wall-psyche,’* a barrier-attitude, with a legalistic outlook; exclusive, possessive, and *profit-making interests*; cold, matter of fact kind of relationships, and every other negative quality that weakens your missionary character. You need to be *constantly self-critical*.

I do admit that if we run a school, we must run it well. So with hospitals. In the field of Education, we must be faithful

to the rules of the Government, rising up to the expectations of the public, performing well in every area where a school is expected to excel (e.g., results, sports, extra-curricular activities). However, all of them must be at the service of the true aim of Education, the *all-round development of the human person*. The specific manner we witness to the Gospel will differ from one place to another, but in every context an *evangelical value-system must prevail* in our institutions, dedicated life-styles, warm relationships, concern for the less privileged, the poor, the marginalized. Hospitals should attend to the *total wellbeing of persons*.

Traditionally, *boarding houses and hostels* were specially meant for the *Catholic formation of young believers*. A Catholic spirit should be created in the mission campus, with traditional prayers, singing, catechism classes, religious competitions of various sorts, retreats, etc.

5.3 Give Greater Attention to Responsive Areas, Communities

In most parts of Asia, where native religions are strong, a change of religion is not easy; in India, it is considered a crime. And yet *impressive Catholic communities have come up* in Korea, many islands of Indonesia, Northeast India, North Myanmar, North Thailand, Vietnam, China, and many tribal pockets of Asia.

Tribal communities (known differently in different places as indigenous people, ethnic minorities, mountain people) seem to say, "Sir, we want to see Jesus" (Jn 12:21). They seem to be eager to know more about Jesus and are *open to the Gospel*. However, even in such situations a stage of initiation may be required. Someone will have to work hard, open out new contacts, share the Message, and follow up those who are interested and those who have embraced the Faith.

With tribal communities, most of our traditional missionary approaches seem to be effective. Methods and approaches that have proven their validity are not be neglected. *Intense pastoral follow-up also is required*. When our collective missionary zeal is placed at the

service of such communities, wonders of growth and deepening of Faith take place.

5.4 The Power of Witness

Criticisms have often been centred round the exercise of authority, the self-righteous tone in which the prophetic role is exercised, *too little evidence of authenticity and commitment*, a simplistic presentation of the Faith (e.g., the image of an intolerant God or a literal understanding of scriptural texts), and a cold, heavy, clerical, pedantic, disciplinary understanding of Church obligations. In this context, an image of humility and sincere readiness to remain open can transform the whole atmosphere. A new culture can emerge.

Modern human listens to witnesses than teachers, to persons whose lives reflect the Gospel: with detachment, selfless dedication, humility, sanctity; examples of missionary zeal like that of Paul, Patrick, Boniface, Xavier, Cyril and Methodius, Damien, *John Paul II, Mother Teresa*; edifying lives of Bishops, Priests, Catechists, educators, and teachers.

Genuineness equips you to dialogue even with those who are inclined towards atheism and extreme secularism. You can join hands with them in issues of *justice, peace*, protection of the environment, and other social concerns.

5.5 The Great Words of Jesus Convince

Miracles do not make an impression on communities that are already over-credulous of the wonders performed by their gurus and deities. But the *teachings of Jesus* always make Asians sit up in amazement. They treasure his words. Jesus had a firm grip on his audience and stirred wonder and admiration in people's hearts, both because of its immediate relevance to the anxieties of the people, and because he addressed the *central concerns of humanity*: love and hatred, anger and forgiveness, joy and suffering, sin and righteousness, truth and freedom, faith and fidelity, religiosity and hypocrisy.

The miracles Jesus performed themselves were “signs,” which meant *actions conveying a message*, e.g., healing of the blind man, cleansing of lepers, multiplication of bread, etc. There was no display, no boast, no arrogance; but purposefulness, meaning, relevance; immediacy, love in action, invitation to faith. Jesus’ love and compassion that led him to uttermost sacrifice is most inspiring.

We spoke of relevance. The Evangelizer’s Message must ‘take flesh’ in human contexts through his/her wholehearted involvement in the life and growth of the community at whose service he/she is. He/she must bring a *human touch to economic and political struggles*, ethical quality to social relationships, and *awareness of the divine to the ‘secular city.’*

The question to be asked in this critical period of history is not whether there is a future for religion, but whether there is a future for humanity without a *religion that provides motivation and hope*; gives balance, stability, purpose; ensures a sense of uprightness; generates love, peace, a sense of responsibility, a spirit of discipline and sacrifice.

6. SHARING THE GOSPEL IN INTIMACY: WHISPERING THE GOSPEL TO THE SOUL OF ASIA

Almost from the beginning of his ministry, Pope Francis had insisted on nothing more than *moving out of “comfort zones”* and reaching out to the “periphery,” to the poor and to the forgotten... in fact, to the furthest limits of human existence. That is what pioneer Missionaries did almost from the beginning. Today we need Evangelizers, who not only cover geographical distances, but who bridge intellectual distances: act as bridge-builders between thoughts, ideologies, philosophies, civilizations.

We are not living in an era merely of a brisk exchange of goods, but intense exchange of ideas. *Civilizations are in dialogue*. Interests clash. Inflated Egos of countries and communities collide. Ideologies are formulated to camouflage partisan interests. Words of peace often hide aggressive intent.

This is the time when people are open to a *message offered in sincerity of purpose* for the emergence of a new phase in human history. This is the time to bypass peripherals and get close to the centre; to ignore the call of the Market and move to the heart of human affairs; to seek *access to the inner chambers of Asian religious earnestness and Whisper the Gospel to the SOUL of Asia...* or of the specific community that you are working for.

The word '*Whispering*' is not used to indicate fear, caution, indifference, or lack of commitment. It stands for *intimacy*. We have studied in earlier sections ways of transcending cultural differences, attending to the central concerns of the civilization (culture, community) of the people to whom you are addressing the Gospel, and identifying yourself with them. A time comes when you are close to the SOUL of a community and a deeper and intimate sharing becomes possible. It may be with a leading person or a prominent few in the community. *Whispering*, therefore, indicates profound respect, *trust, closeness, intimacy, mutuality, and depth*. In Asia, *sacred mysteries* are taught in contexts of closeness and sacred words (*Sutras*) are pronounced in an atmosphere of reverence and seriousness.

Paul says, "I have complete confidence in the Gospel" (Rom 1:16). When Jesus touches the *Inner Genius* of a community (culture, civilization) with the Message of the Gospel, it is not only strengthened, it is *made to flower*; it is transformed and moves towards greater perfection.

There is *Joy* in sharing such a life-giving Message. May that be our experience.